

**TRIPLE BERNSTEIN STANCU OPERATOR OF ROUGH λ -
STATISTICAL CONVERGENCE IN PROBABILITY AND ITS A
SUMMABILITY OF NEUTROSOPHIC METRIC SPACES**

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we propose a new approach to extend the application area of rough statistical convergence usually used in the triple sequence of Bernstein stancu operator of real numbers to the theory of probability distributions. In this concept probability introduction Bernstein stancu polynomials of rough λ - statistical convergence and Bernstein stancu polynomials of rough strong (V, λ) - summable generalize the convergence analysis to accommodate any form of distribution of random variables and discuss general properties and interrelations of above mentioned convergences are investigated and some observations are made in these classes and in this way we show that rough statistical convergence in probability is the more generalized concept than usual Bernstein stancu polynomials of rough statistical convergence in neutrosophic metric spaces are examined. Second, we define the statistical summability A of the Bernstein stancu polynomials of the summability RH matrix and prove that it is stronger than Bernstein stancu polynomials A rough statistical convergence of neutrosophic metric spaces if admissible then $I_{\lambda}^g - LIM^{\theta} B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \neq \phi$. The theory of statistical convergence has been discussed in trigonometric series, summability theory, measure theory, turnpike theory, approximation theory, fuzzy set theory, and so on.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The asymptotic density is one of the possibilities to measure how large a subset is of the set of natural numbers. We know intuitively that positive integers are much more than perfect squares. That is why every perfect square is positive and many other positive integers exist besides this one; however, the set of positive integers is not in fact larger than the set of perfect squares. Both sets are infinite and countable and can therefore be put in one to one correspondence. Nevertheless, if one goes through the in this case, natural density helps us and makes this intuition precise.

Let α be a subset of a positive integer. We consider the interval $[1, n]$ and randomly select an integer in this interval. Then, the ratio of the number of elements in $\alpha \cap [1, n]$ to the total number of elements in $[1, n]$ is probably belongs to α , for $n \rightarrow \infty$, if this probability exists, that is this probability tends to some limit, then this limit is used as the asymptotic density of the set α . This mentions us that the asymptotic density is a kind of probability of choosing a number from the set α .

The set of positive integers will denoted by Z^+ . Let α and β be subsets of Z^+ . If the symmetric difference $\alpha \Delta \beta$ is finite, then we can say α is asymptotically equal to β and denote $\alpha \approx \beta$. Freedman and Sember have introduced the concept of a lower asymptotic density and defined a concept of convergence in density.

Aytar[23] studied rough statistical convergence and defined the set of rough statistical limit points of a sequence and obtain to statistical convergence criteria associated with this set and proved that this set is closed and convex. In addition, Aytar[24] studied that the r -limit set of the sequence is equal to the intersection of these sets and that the r -core of the sequence is equal to the union of these sets. Dündar and cakan[36-38] investigated the rough ideal and defined the set of rough ideal limit points of a sequence. The notion of I -convergence of a triple sequence, which is based on the structure of the ideal I of subsets of $N \times N \times N$, where N is the of all natural numbers, is a natural generalization of the notion of convergence and statistical convergence, and also Zhan et al [39,40] studied various rough sets.

Our main interest in the present chapter is to obtain a general Korovkin-type approximation theorem for triple sequences of positive linear operators of two variables from $H_w(K)$ to $C_w(K)$ via statistical A summability.

In probability theory, a new type of convergence called statistical convergence in probability was introduced in Ghosal, as follows. Let $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ be a triple sequence of the Bernstein stancu operator of random variables where each $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ is defined on the same sample spaces W , for each m, n, k with respect to a given class of events Δ and a given probability function $P : \Delta \rightarrow R^3$. Then the triple sequence of Bernstein stancu operator of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ is said to be statistical convergence in probability to a random variable $(B_{mnk}(f, x)) ; W \rightarrow R^3$ if for any $\epsilon > 0, \delta > 0$

$$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{uvw} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : P(B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x) \geq \delta)\}| = 0. \quad (1.1)$$

In this case, we write $B_{mnk}(f, x) \xrightarrow{S^P} f(x)$. The class of all triple sequences of Bernstein operator of random variables that are statistical convergence in probability is denoted by S^P .

Let $\lambda = (\lambda_{uvw})$ be a non-decreasing triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of positive numbers tending to ∞ such that $\lambda_{u,v,w+1} \leq \lambda_{uvw} + 1, \lambda_{111} = 1$. The collection of all such triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of λ is denoted by D .

The generalized Delavalee'-poussin mean f be a continuous function defined on the closed interval $[0,1]$. A triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of real numbers is defined by $t_{uvw}(x) = \frac{\lambda_{uvw}}{Q_{uvw}} \sum_{(m,n,k) \in Q_{uvw}} B_{mnk}(f, x)$, where $Q_{uvw} = [(uvw) - \lambda_{uvw} + 1, (uvw)]$. A triple sequence Bernstein polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of real numbers is said to be $[V, \lambda]$ - summable to $f(x)$, if $\lim t_{uvw}(f, x) = f(x)$.

Let A be a three dimensional summability matrix. For a given triple sequence $x = (x_{mnk})$, the transform A transform of x , denoted by $Ax := (Ax)_{ij\ell}$ given by

$$(Ax)_{ij\ell} = \sum_{(m,n,k) \in N^3} a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k} x_{mnk} \tag{1.2}$$

provided the triple series converges in Prinsheim's sense [8] for every $(i, j, \ell) \in N^3$.

A three dimensional matrix $Ax := (Ax)_{ij\ell}$ is said to be RH-regular it maps every bounded P -convergent sequence into a P -convergent sequence with the same P -limit. A three dimensional matrix $Ax := (Ax)_{ij\ell}$ is RH regular if and only if

- (1) $P - \lim_{i,j,\ell} \sum_{(m,n,k) \in N^3} a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k} = 0$ for each $m, n, k \in N^3$,
- (2) $P - \lim_{i,j,\ell} \sum_{(m,n,k) \in N^3} a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k} = 0$ for each $m, n, k \in N^3$,
- (3) $P - \lim_{i,j,\ell} \sum_{m \in N^3} a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k} = 0$ for each $n, k \in N^3$,
- (4) $P - \lim_{i,j,\ell} \sum_{n \in N^3} a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k} = 0$ for each $m, k \in N^3$,
- (5) $P - \lim_{i,j,\ell} \sum_{k \in N^3} a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k} = 0$ for each $m, n \in N^3$,
- (6) $\sum_{(m,n,k) \in N^3} |a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k}|$ is P -convergent for every $(i, j, \ell) \in N^3$,
- (7) there exist finite positive integers A and B such that $\sum_{m,n,k > B} |a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k}| < A$ holds for every $(i, j, \ell) \in N^3$.

Now let $A = a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k}$ be a non-negative RH-regular summability matrix, and $K \subset N^3$. Then the A -density of K is given by

$$\delta_2^A(K) : P - \lim_{i,j,\ell} \sum_{(m,n,k) \in K(\epsilon)} a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k}, \text{ where } K(\epsilon) = \{(m, n, k) \in N^3 : |x_{mnk} - \ell| \geq \epsilon\} \tag{1.3}$$

provided that the limit on the right hand side exists in Pringsheim's sense. A real triple sequence $x = (x_{mnk})$ is said to be A -statistically convergent to a number L if for every $\epsilon > 0$.

$$\delta_2^A = \{(m, n, k) \in N^3 : |x_{mnk} - \ell| \geq \epsilon\} = 0. \tag{1.4}$$

In this case, we write $st_2 - \lim_{m,n,k} = \ell$. Let K be a subset of the set of positive integers $N \times N \times N$ and let us denote the set

$$K_{ij\ell} = \{(m, n, k) \in K : m \geq i, n \leq j, k \leq \ell\}. \tag{1.5}$$

Then the natural density of K is given by

$$\delta(K) = \lim_{i,j,\ell \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|K_{i,j,\ell}|}{ij\ell} \tag{1.6}$$

where $|K_{i,j,\ell}|$ denotes the number of elements in $K_{i,j,\ell}$.

The Bernstein operator of order (r, s, t) is given by

$$B_{rst}(f, x) = \sum_{m=0}^r \sum_{n=0}^s \sum_{k=0}^t f \binom{r}{m} \binom{s}{n} \binom{t}{k} x^{m+n+k} (1-x)^{(m-r)+(n-s)+(k-t)} \tag{1.7}$$

where f is the continuous function (real or complex valued) defined in $[0, 1]$.

Throughout the paper, R denotes the real of three dimensional space with metric (X, d) . Consider a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials $(B_{m,n,k}(f, x))$ such that $(B_{m,n,k}(f, x)) \in R, m, n, k \in N^3$. Let f be a continuous function defined in the corresponding interval $[0, 1]$. A triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials $(B_{rst}(f, x))$ is said to be statistically convergent to $0 \in R$, written as $st - \lim x = 0$, provided that the se is

$$K_\epsilon = \{(m, n, k) \in N^3 : |B_{m,n,k}(f, x) - f(x)| \geq \epsilon\} \tag{1.8}$$

has natural density zero for any $\epsilon > 0$. In this case, 0 is called the statistical limit of the triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials. i.e. $\delta(K_\epsilon) = 0$. That is,

$$\lim_{rst \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{pqj} |\{(m, n, k) \leq (p, q, j) : |B_{m,n,k}(f, x) - f(x)| \geq \epsilon\}| = 0. \tag{1.9}$$

In this case, we write $\delta - \lim B_{m,n,k}(f, x) = f(x)$ or $B_{m,n,k}(f, x) \rightarrow^{Sb} f(x)$. A subset A of N^3 is said to have asymptotic density $d(A)$ if

$$d(A) = \lim_{ij\ell \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{ij\ell} \sum_{m=1}^i \sum_{n=1}^j \sum_{k=1}^\ell \chi_A(K). \tag{1.10}$$

A triple sequence (real or complex) can be defined as a function of $x : N \times N \times N \rightarrow R(C)$, where N, R and C denote the set of natural numbers, real numbers, and complex numbers, respectively. The different types of notions of triple sequence were introduced and investigated at the beginning by [1,7] and many others.

A triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials is said to be triple Bernstein stancu polynomials of analytic if

$$\sup_{m,n,k} |B_{m,n,k}(f, x) - f(x)|^{\frac{1}{m+n+k}} < \infty \tag{1.11}$$

The spaces of all triple Bernstein stancu polynomials of analytic sequences are usually denoted by Λ^3_B

Zadeh [1] was the first to introduce the theory of fuzzy sets. It has a profound impact on all scientific fields and is quite necessary for real-life situations.

Atanossov[2] generalized the concept of fuzzy sets known as intuitionistic fuzzy sets. One of the dominant problems in fuzzy topology is to obtain an appropriate hypothesis of the fuzzy metric spaces. Moreover, Park[3] applied George and Veeramani's [4] idea of using the t-norm and the t-conorm to fuzzy metric spaces for defining intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces and studying their fundamental properties. After a while, Smarandache [5] introduced the notion of neutrosophic sets, which is a different kind of notion in classical set theory by adding an intermediate membership function. This set is a formal setting that attempts to measure that truth, indeterminacy, and falsehood. Smarandache [6] further studied the differences between the intuitionistic fuzzy set and the neutrosophic set and the corresponding relations between these two sets. The basic differences are as follows:

(1) Neutrosophic set can distinguish between relative truth equal to 1 and absolute truth equal to 1^+ . This has application in philosophy. For this reason, the unitary standard interval $[0,1]$ used in intuitionistic fuzzy set has been extended to the unitary non-standard interval $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ in a neutrosophic set.

(2) In the neutrosophic set, there is no condition on T (Truth), H (Indeterminacy) and F (Falsehood) other than they are subsets of $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$, therefore:

$$^{-}0 \leq \inf T + \inf H + \inf F \leq \sup T + \sup H + \sup F \leq 3^{+}.$$

(3) In neutrosophic sets, the components T (Truth), H (Indeterminacy) and F (Falsehood) can also be non standard subsets included in the unitary non standard interval $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ not only standard subsets included in the unitary standard interval $[0,1]$ as in intuitionistic fuzzy logic.

Neutrosophic sets are more effective and flexible because they handle not only independent components, but also partially dependent and partially independent components, while intuitionistic fuzzy sets cannot deal with them. In addition, Smarandache [7-9] investigated the neutro algebra which is a generalization of the partial algebra. Neutro algebraic structures and anti algebraic structures. Moreover, Bera and Mahapatra [10] defined neutrosophic soft linear spaces[NSNLS]. In [10] neutrosophic norm, Cauchy sequence in [NSNLS], the convexity of NSNLS and the convexity metric in NSNLS were studied. There has been considerable progress in the study of neutrosophic theory in various fields by different authors.

Fast [11] proposed the concepts of statistical convergence that were later studied by many researchers. Friday and Orhan [12] have investigated the theory of lupinary statistical convergence. Later, the concepts of statistical convergence of double sequences have been analysed in IFNS by Mursaleen and Mohiuddin [13]. Quite recently Kirisci and Simsek [14] introduced the notion of neutrosophic normed space and statistical convergence. Since neutrosophic normed space is a natural generalization of IFNS and statistical convergence. Neutrosophic set and neutrosophic logic has used by applied sciences and theoretical science such as decision making, robotics, summability theory.

One first presents the evolution of sets from a fuzzy set to neutrosophic set. Then we introduce the Neutrosophic components T,F,I which present the membership indeterminacy and the non-membership value, respectively, where $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ is the non-standard unit interval, and thus one defines the neutrosophic set. One

gives examples from mathematics, physics, philosophy and applications of the neutrosophic set. Afterwards, one introduces the neutrosophic set operations (complements, intersections, union, difference, cartesian product, inclusion, and n-ary relationship).

The fuzzy set (FS) was introduced by Zadeh [1] in 1965, where each element had a degree of membership (t).

The intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) in a universe X was introduced by K. Atanassov [2] in 1986 as a generalization of FS, where, in addition to the degree of membership $\mu_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ of each element $x \in X$ in a set degree of non-membership $\nu_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ such that $\forall x \in X, \mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1$.

The Neutrosophic set (NS) was introduced by F.Samarandache, who introduced the degree of indeterminacy (I) an independent component in his 1995 manuscript published in 1998.

According to Deschrijver and Kerne (2003) the vague set defined by Gau and Buehrer (1993) was proved by Bustine and Burillo (1996) to be the same as IFS.

Goguen (1967) defined the L-fuzzy set in X as a mapping $X \rightarrow L$ such that (L^*, \leq_L) is a complete lattice, where $L^* = \{(x_1, x_2) \in [0, 1]^2, x_1 + x_2 \leq 1\}$ and $(x_1, x_2) \leq_{L^*} (y_1, y_2) \Leftrightarrow x_1 \leq y_1$ and $x_2 \geq y_2$. The interval-valued fuzzy sets (IVFS) apparently first studied by Sambuc (1975) which were called gray sets and IFS by Dens (1989) are specific kinds of L-fuzzy sets.

According to Cornelis et al. (2003), Gehrke et al. (1996) stated that many people believe that assigning an exact member to an expert's opinion is too restrictive and the assignment of an interval of values is more realistic which is somehow similar with the imprecise probability theory where instead of a crisp probability one has as interval (upper and lower) probabilities as in Walley (1991).

Atanassov (1999) defined the intuitionistic fuzzy set (IVIFS) on a universe X as an object A such that $A = \{(x, M_A(x), N_A(x)), x \in X\}$ (2)

with $M_A : X \rightarrow \text{Int}([0, 1])$ and $N_A : X \rightarrow \text{Int}([0, 1])$ (3)

and $\forall x \in X, \text{Sup}M_A(x) + \text{Sup}N_A(x) \leq 1$. (4)

Belnap (1977) defined a four-valued logic with truth (T), false (F), unknown (U) and contradiction (C). He used a bilattice in which the four components were inter-related

In 1995, starting from philosophy (when I fretted to distinguish between absolute truth and relative truth or between absolute falsehood and relative falsehood in logics and, respectively, between absolute membership and relative membership and absolute non-membership and relative non-membership in set theory) I began the non-standard analysis, by order to combine the non-standard analysis with a tri-component logic/ set/ probability theory and with Philosophy (I was excited

by Paradoxism in science and arts and letters as well as by para consistency and completeness in knowledge). How to deal with all of them at once, is it possible to unite them?

I proposed the term "Neutrosophic" because "Neutrosophic" etymologically comes from "Neutrosophy" [French retire i Latin Neuter, neutral and GreekSophia, skill / wisdom] which means knowledge of neutral thought, and this third/ neutral represents the main distinction between "Fuzzy"/ "intuitionistic fuzzy" logic /set and "neutrosophic" logic/set, ie. the included middle component (Lupasco- Nicolscu's logic in philosophy), ie. the neutral/ indeterminate/ unknown part (besides the "truth"/ "membership" and "falsehood"/ "non-membership" components that both appear in fuzzy logic/set.

2. DEFINITIONS AND PRELIMINARIES OF NEUTROSOPHIC SET

Fuzziness, intuitionistic fuzziness, and neutrosophy are defined as follows: The fuzzy subset F of R is known as the fuzzy number (FN). The FN is a mapping $F : R \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that links each real number a to the degree of membership $F(a)$. Let F be FN. Next, it is known that

- (1) For $a_0 \in R$, F is viewed as normal if $F(a_0) = 1$.
- (2) For any $\mu > 0$, $F^{-1}\{[0, r + \mu]\}$ that is open in the standard topology $\forall \tau \in [0, 1]$,
 F is considered upper.
- (3) The τ -cuts of F are characterized as the set $[F]^\tau = \{a \in R : F(a) \geq \tau\}$, $\tau \in [0, 1]$.

Let F be a non-empty set. An IFS in F is an object U defined by $U = \langle a, G_U(a), Y_U(a) \rangle : a \in F$, where $G_U(a) : F \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $Y_U(a) : F \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are functions of any $a \in F$ such that

$0 \leq G_U(a) + Y_U(a) \leq 1$. Let U be an IFN. Then

- (1) An IF subset of the R .
- (2) If $G_U(a_0) = 1$ and $Y_U(a_0) = 0$ for $a_0 \in R$, normal,
- (3) The membership function (MF) $G_U(a)$ is said to be convex if $(G_U(\lambda a_1 + (1 - \lambda)a_2) \geq \min(G_U(a_1), G_U(a_2)))$,
 $\forall a_1, a_2 \in R$ and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$.
- (4) The non membership function (NMF) $Y_U(a)$ is concave if $(Y_U(\lambda a_1 + (1 - \lambda)a_2) \geq \min(Y_U(a_1), Y_U(a_2)))$,
 $\forall a_1, a_2 \in R$ and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$.
- (5) Y_U is lower semi-continuous and G_U is upper semi-continuous.
- (6) The bounded set $\text{Supp}u = \text{cl}\{a \in F : Y_U(a) < 1\}$.

An IFS $U = \langle a, G_U(a), Y_U(a) \rangle : a \in F$ such that $G_U(a)$ and $1 - Y_U(a)$ are FNS, where $(1 - Y_U)(a) = 1 - Y_U(a)$ and $G_U(a) + Y_U(a) \leq 1$ is called IFN.

Let us consider that F is a space of points (objects). Denote $G_U(a)$ as truth-MF, $B_U(a)$ is an indeterminacy-MF and $Y_U(a)$ is a falsity-MF, where U is a set in F with $a \in F$. Then, if we take the following

$$I =]0^-, 1^+[$$

$$G_U(a) : F \rightarrow I,$$

$$B_U(a) : F \rightarrow I,$$

$$Y_U(a) : F \rightarrow I,$$

There is no restriction on the sum of $G_U(a)$, $B_U(a)$ and $Y_U(a)$.

$$\text{Therefore, } 0^- \leq \sup G_U(a) + \sup B_U(a) + \sup Y_U(a) \leq 3^+.$$

The set U consisting of $G_U(a)$, $B_U(a)$ and $Y_U(a)$ in F is called a Neutrosophic set (NS) and can be denoted by

$$U = \{ \langle a, (G_U(a), B_U(a), Y_U(a)) \rangle : a \in F, G_U(a), B_U(a), Y_U(a) \in I \} \quad (2.1)$$

Clearly, NS is an enhancement of $[0,1]$ of IFS.

An NS U is included in another NS V , ($U \subseteq V$), if and only if $\inf G_U(a) \leq \inf G_V(a)$, $\sup G_U(a) \leq \sup G_V(a)$,

$$\inf B_U(a) \geq \inf B_V(a), \sup B_U(a) \geq \sup B_V(a),$$

$$\inf Y_U(a) \geq \inf Y_V(a), \sup Y_U(a) \geq \sup Y_V(a),$$

for any $a \in F$. However, NS is not comfortable to practice in real problems. According to Ye, a simplification of an NS U in (2.1) is

$$U = \{ \langle a, G_U(a), B_U(a), Y_U(a) \rangle : a \in F \}$$

which is called a simplified NS. Particularly if F has only one element $\langle G_U(a), B_U(a), Y_U(a) \rangle$ is said to be a simplified NN. Expressly, we may see simplified NS as a subclass of NS.

The definitions of simplified neutrosophic set (SNS), TN, and TCN are adopted and slightly adapted from [12] for the purpose of this study.

Let T, I, F be real standard or non standard subsets of $]^-0, 1^+]$, with

$$\text{Sup}T = t.\text{sup}, \text{inf}T = t.\text{inf}$$

$$\text{Sup}I = t.\text{sup}, \text{inf}I = t.\text{inf}$$

$$\text{Sup}F = t.\text{sup}, \text{inf}F = t.\text{inf}$$

$$\text{and } n.\text{sup} = t.\text{sup} + i.\text{sup} + f.\text{sup},$$

$$n.\text{inf} = t.\text{inf} + i.\text{inf} + f.\text{inf}$$

T, I, F are called Neutrosophic components.

Let U be a universe of discourse and M a set included in U . An element x from U is noted with respect to the set M as $x(T, I, F)$ and belongs to M in the following way : it is $t\%$ true in the set, $i\%$ in indeterminate (unknown if it is) in the set and

f% false, where t varies in T, i varies in I, f varies in F.

For software engineering proposals, the classical unit interval [0,1] is used. For single valued Neutrosophic logic (t, i, f), the sum of the components is $0 \leq t+i+f \leq 3$ when all three components are independent.

$0 \leq t + i + f \leq 2$ when two components are dependent, while the third one is independent from them.

$0 \leq t + i + f \leq 1$ when three components are dependent, when three or two of the components t, i, f are independent, there is room for incomplete information (sum < 1), paraconsistent and contradictory information (sum > 1) or complete information (sum = 1). In general, the sum of two components x and y that vary in the unitary interval [0,1] is $0 \leq x+y \leq 2 - d^0(x, y)$ where $d^0(x, y)$ is the degree of dependence between x and y. Therefore $2 - d^0(x, y)$ is the degree of independence between x and y.

Definition 2.1. A standard bipolar Neutrosophic set A is defined as

$$A = \{ \langle x, T^+(x), I^+(x), f^+(x), T^-(x), I^-(x), f^-(x) \rangle / x \in X \}.$$

where $T^+, I^+, F^+ : x \rightarrow [0, 1]$
and $T^-, I^-, F^- : x \rightarrow [-1, 0]$

Definition 2.2. In order to make distribution between classical (Boolean) logic/set, fuzzy logic/set and Neutrosophic logic/set, we denote their corresponding operators (negation/complement, conjunction/ intersection, disjunction/ union, implication, and equivalence) as follows:

(1) For classical (Boolean) logic/set :

$$\neg \quad \wedge \quad \vee \quad \rightarrow \quad \leftrightarrow$$

(2) For fuzzy logic/ set :

$$\neg \quad \wedge \quad \vee \quad \rightarrow \quad \leftrightarrow$$

$$F \quad F \quad F \quad F \quad F$$

(3) For intuitionistic fuzzy logic/set :

$$\neg \quad \wedge \quad \vee \quad \rightarrow \quad \leftrightarrow$$

IF IF IF IF IF

(4) For neutrosophic logic/set:

$\neg \quad \wedge \quad \vee \quad \rightarrow \quad \leftrightarrow$

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Definition 2.3. The Neutrosophic set operations (complement, intersection, union, difference, cartesian product, A is a subset of B , neutrosophic n -ary relation, neutrosophic quantifiers and implications) are defined as follows:

Let the two sets A and B over the universe U , $x = x(T_1, I_1, F_1) \in A$ and $x = x(T_2, I_2, F_2) \in B$ indeterminacy and non-membership respectively appurtenance and similarly $y = y(T^1, I^1, F^1) \in B$. If after calculations in the below operations one obtains values < 0 or > 1 , then one replaces them with $^-0$ or $^+1$ respectively.

Definition 2.4. Give an operation $\star : [0, 1]^2 \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$. If the operation \star is satisfying the following conditions, then it is called that the operation \star is continuous $TN : \text{For } s, t, u, v \in [0, 1]$,

- (1) $s \star 1 = s$.
- (2) If $s \leq u$ and $t \leq v$, then so $t \leq u \star v$,
- (3) \star is continuous.
- (4) \star is commutative and associative.

Definition 2.5. Give an operation $\cdot : [0, 1]^2 \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$. If the operation \cdot is satisfying the following conditions, then it is called that the operation \cdot is continuous $TC :$

- (1) $s \cdot 1 = s$.
- (2) If $s \leq u$ and $t \leq v$, then so $t \leq u \cdot v$,
- (3) \cdot is continuous.
- (4) \cdot is commutative and associative.

If $0 < \epsilon_i < 1, i=1$ to $7, \star$ and \cdot are the continuous t-norm respectively. Then if we choose $0 < \epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 < 1$ for $\epsilon_1 > \epsilon_2$, then there exist $0 < \epsilon_3, \epsilon_4 < 0, 1$ such that $\epsilon_1 \star \epsilon_3 \geq \epsilon_2, \epsilon_1 \geq \epsilon_4 \cdot \epsilon_2$.

Further, if we choose $\epsilon_5 \in (0, 1)$,

Then there exist $\epsilon_6, \epsilon_7 \in (0, 1)$ such that $\epsilon_6 * \epsilon_6 \geq \epsilon_5$ and $\epsilon_7 \cdot \epsilon_7 \leq \epsilon_5$.

Example: Example : Let (F, d) be a MS. Give the operations \circ and \cdot as default $(\min)T N a \circ b = \min\{a, b\}$ and default $(\max)T C a \cdot b = \max\{a, b\}$

$$G(a, b, \lambda) = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + d(a, b)},$$

$$B(a, b, \lambda) = \frac{d(a, b)}{\lambda + d(a, b)},$$

$Y(a, b, \lambda) = \frac{d(a, b)}{\lambda}$; $\forall a, b \in F$ and $\lambda > 0$. For fixed $a \neq b$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$, $Y(a, b, \lambda) \rightarrow \infty$ which violates the co-domain $[0, 1]$. Also $B(a, b, \lambda) \rightarrow 1$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$ and $B(a, b, \lambda) \rightarrow 0$ as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ but condition (12) $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} B(a, b, \lambda) = 0 (\forall \lambda > 0)$

Condition (18) \Rightarrow If $\lambda \leq 0$ then $G(a, b, \lambda) = 1, B(a, b, \lambda) = 0, Y(a, b, \lambda) = 0$.

Definition 2.6. Let V be a NMS, the triple sequence $x = (x_{mnk})$ in V $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $\lambda > 0$. Then the triple sequence $x_{mnk} \rightarrow x, N \in \mathbb{N}^3$ such that

$$G(x_{mnk}, x, \lambda) > 1 - \epsilon; B(x_{mnk}, x, \lambda) < \epsilon; Y(x_{mnk}, x, \lambda) < \epsilon$$

that is $\lim_{m,n,k \rightarrow \infty} G(x_{mnk}, x, \lambda) = 1; \lim_{m,n,k \rightarrow \infty} B(x_{mnk}, x, \lambda) = 0;$

$\lim_{m,n,k \rightarrow \infty} Y(x_{mnk}, x, \lambda) = 0$ as $\lambda > 0$.

In this case, the triple sequence x_{mnk} is called a convergent sequence in V . The convergence in NMS is denoted by $N - \lim_{mnk \rightarrow \infty} x_{mnk} = 1$.

3. TRIPLE BERNSTEIN STANCU OPERATOR OF ROUGH λ - STATISTICAL CONVERGENCE IN PROBABILITY OF NEUTROSOPHIC METRIC SPACES

Definition 3.1. Take F be an arbitrary set, $\mathbf{N} = \{< a, G_U(a), B_U(a), Y_U(a) > : a \in F\}$ be neutrosophic metric spaces such that $\mathbf{N} : F \times F \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$. Let \circ and \cdot show the continuous TN and continuous TC, respectively. The four tuple $(F, \mathbf{N}, \circ, \cdot)$ is called Neutrosophic metric space (NMS) when the following conditions are satisfied $\forall a, b, c \in F$.

- (1) $0 \leq G(a, b, \lambda) \leq 1, 0 \leq B(a, b, \lambda) \leq 1, 0 \leq Y(a, b, \lambda) \leq 1, \forall \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$,
- (2) $G(a, b, \lambda) + B(a, b, \lambda) + Y(a, b, \lambda) \leq 3$ (for $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$),
- (3) $G(a, b, \lambda) = 1$ (for $\lambda > 0$)
 $\Leftrightarrow a = b$
- (4) $G(a, b, \lambda) = G(b, a, \lambda)$ (for $\lambda > 0$),
- (5) $G(a, b, \lambda) \circ G(b, c, \mu) \leq G(a, c, \lambda + \mu)$ ($\forall \lambda, \mu > 0$)
- (6) $G(a, b, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.
- (7) $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} G(a, b, \lambda) = 1$ ($\forall \lambda > 0$)
- (8) $B(a, b, \lambda) = 0$ ($\forall \lambda > 0$)
 $\Leftrightarrow a = b$
- (9) $B(a, b, \lambda) = B(b, a, \lambda)$ (for $\lambda > 0$),
- (10) $B(a, b, \lambda) \cdot B(b, c, \mu) \leq B(a, c, \lambda + \mu)$ ($\forall \lambda, \mu > 0$)
- (11) $B(a, b, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.
- (12) $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} B(a, b, \lambda) = 0$ ($\forall \lambda > 0$)

- (13) $Y(a, b, \lambda) = 0 (\forall \lambda > 0)$
 $\Leftrightarrow a = b$
- (14) $Y(a, b, \lambda) = Y(b, a, \lambda)$ (for $\lambda > 0$),
- (15) $Y(a, b, \lambda) \cdot Y(b, c, \mu) \leq Y(a, c, \lambda + \mu) (\forall \lambda, \mu > 0)$
- (16) $Y(a, b, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.
- (17) $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} Y(a, b, \lambda) = 0$ for $(\lambda > 0)$,
- (18) If $\lambda \leq 0$, then $G(a, b, \lambda) = 0, B(a, b, \lambda) = 1, Y(a, b, \lambda) = 1$.

The Neutrosophic Metric (NM) on F is therefore denoted by $N = (G, B, Y)$. The degree of proximity, neutrality, and non-nearness between a and b with respect to λ are represented by the functions $G(a, b, \lambda), B(a, b, \lambda)$, and $Y(a, b, \lambda)$.

A function $X : N \times N \times N \rightarrow R(C)$ is a triple sequence (real or complex), where N, R, and C represent the sets of natural numbers, real numbers and complex numbers, respectively. Esi et al.[14,15] and Subramanian et al. [16-18] were the first to present and study the various concepts of triple sequence. Hazarika et al. [19] and numerous others.

Let $x = (x_{m,n,k})$ be a triple sequence of complex or real numbers. The series $\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} x_{m,n,k}$ is called a triple series. If and only if the triple sequence $(S_{m,n,k}) = \sum_{i,j,q=1}^{(m,n,k)} x_{ijq} ((m, n, k) = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$, then the triple series is considered convergent.

A triple sequence $x = (x_{m,n,k})$ is considered analytic if $\sup_{m,n,k} |x_{m,n,k}|^{\frac{1}{m+n+k}} < \infty$. Typically, Λ^3 is used to represent the vector space of all triple analytic sequences. If $|x_{m,n,k}|^{\frac{1}{m+n+k}} \rightarrow 0$ as $m, n, k \rightarrow \infty$, then a triple sequence $(x_{m,n,k})$ is referred to as a triple entire sequence. Γ^3 is typically used to represent the vector space of all complete triple sequences. Let Λ^3 be the set of sequences having this property, and Γ^3 be a metric space with the metric $d(x, y) = \sup_{m,n,k} \{ |x_{m,n,k} - y_{m,n,k}|^{\frac{1}{m+n+k}} : m, n, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \}$ for all $x = (x_{m,n,k})$ and $y = (y_{m,n,k})$ in Γ^3 . Let $\phi = \{ \text{finite sequences} \}$.

Definition 3.2. Let (F, N, \circ, \cdot) be an NMS of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ in the universe of discourse U, (ie.,)

$AN_{MV} = \{ \langle x, G_{UMNV}(x, \beta), B_{UMNV}(x, \beta), Y_{UMNV}(x, \beta) \rangle : x \in U \}$
 the membership function is defined as

$$G_{UMNV}(x, \beta) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon)$$

$$B_{UMNV}(x, \beta) \geq \beta + \epsilon \text{ and}$$

$$Y_{UMNV}(x, \beta) \geq \beta + \epsilon$$

where (1) $G^+ = 1 - Y^-$ (2) $Y^+ = 1 - G^-$ and (3) $0 \leq G^- + B^- + Y^- \leq 2$.

Definition 3.3. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough λ - statistical convergence in probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ on the universe of discourse F, a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{m,n,k}(f, x))$ of a real numbers of continuous function defined on the closed interval $[0, 1]$ is said to be neutrosophic metric spaces of strong $[V, \lambda]$ summable to $f(x)$ with respect to the roughness of degree β (or shortly $[V, \lambda]$ -converges to $f(x)$), there exist $(u, v, w) \in N^3$

such that

$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{uvw}} (\mu(|(B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))| \geq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon)) = 1$ or
 $(\gamma(|(B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))| \leq (\beta + \epsilon)) = 0$ for all $m \geq u, n \geq v, k \geq w$. and we denote by $B_{mnk}(f, x) \xrightarrow{[V, \lambda]} f(x)$ or $B_{mnk}(f, x) \rightarrow^{[V, \lambda]} f(x)$.

Definition 3.4. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough λ - statistical convergence in probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ on the universe of discourse F , a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of a real numbers of continuous function defined on the closed interval $[0, 1]$ is said to be neutrosophic metric spaces of λ statistically convergent to $f(x)$ with respect to the roughness of degree β (or shortly β - converges to (f, x) such that

$\lim_{m, n, k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{mnk}} (\mu(|(B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))| \geq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon)) = 1$ or

$\lim_{m, n, k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{mnk}} (\gamma(|(B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))| \leq (\beta + \epsilon)) = 0$

for all $m \geq u, n \geq v, k \geq w$. and we denote by $B_{mnk}(f, x) \xrightarrow{\beta^{\lambda}} f(x)$ or $B_{mnk}(f, x) \rightarrow_{\beta}^{\lambda} f(x)$ if we take $\beta = 0$, then we obtain the ordinary convergence.

Definition 3.5. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough λ - statistical convergence in probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ on the universe of discourse F , a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of a real numbers of continuous function defined on the closed interval $[0, 1]$ is said to be neutrosophic metric spaces of triple sequences of rough λ - statistically convergent in probability to a random variable $(B_{mnk}(f, x)) : W \rightarrow R^3$ with respect to the roughness of degree β (or shortly $\beta - \lambda$ - summable in probability to $f(x)$) if for each $\epsilon > 0, \delta > 0$.

$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{uvw}} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\mu(P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x) |)) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta\}| = 1$

or

$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{uvw}} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\gamma(P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x) |)) \geq (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta\}| = 0$.

$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{uvw}} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\mu(1 - P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x) |)) \geq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta\}| = 1$.

or equivalently

$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{uvw}} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\gamma(1 - P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x) |)) \leq (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta\}| = 0$. and we write $B_{mnk}(f, x) \xrightarrow{\beta^{\lambda}} f(x)$. or $B_{mnk}(f, x) \rightarrow_{\beta}^{\lambda} f(x)$. The class of all β neutrosophic metric spaces of statistically convergent triple sequences of Bernstein stancu polynomials of random variables in probability will be simply denoted by βS_{λ}^p .

Definition 3.6. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough λ - statistical convergence in probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ on the universe of discourse F , a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of a real numbers of continuous function defined on the closed interval $[0, 1]$ is said to be neutrosophic metric spaces of triple sequences of rough $[V, \lambda]$ - summable in probability to a random variable $(B_{mnk}(f, x)) : W \rightarrow R^3$ with respect to the roughness

of degree β (or shortly $\beta - \lambda$ - summable in probability to $f(x)$) if for each $\epsilon > 0$.

$$\lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{u,v,w}} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\mu(P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon)\}| = 1$$

or

$$\lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_{u,v,w}} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\gamma(P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))) \geq (\beta + \epsilon)\}| = 0.$$

$$\lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{u,v,w} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\mu(1 - P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))) \geq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon)\}| = 1.$$

or equivalently

$$\lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{u,v,w} |\{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\gamma(1 - P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))) \leq (\beta + \epsilon)\}| = 0.$$

and we write $B_{mnk}(f, x) \rightarrow_{\beta, \lambda}^{[\gamma, \lambda]} f(x)$. or $B_{mnk}(f, x) \rightarrow_{\beta, \lambda}^{[\mu, \lambda]} f(x)$. The class of all β neutrosophic metric spaces of $[V, \lambda]$ summable triple sequences of Bernstein stancu polynomials of random variables in probability will be simply denoted by $\beta[V, \lambda]^P$.

Definition 3.7. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough λ - statistical convergence in probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ on the universe of discourse F , a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of a real numbers of continuous function defined on the closed interval $[0,1]$ and $A = (a_{i,j,\ell,m,n,k})$ be a non-negative regular summability matrix of a neutrosophic metric spaces of triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ is said to be neutrosophic metric spaces of rough statistically A summable convergent to $f(x)$ denoted by $B_{mnk}(f, x) \rightarrow_{\text{sta}^{-\lim x}} f(x)$, if for every $\epsilon > 0$ provided that the set

$$\delta_2 \{(m, n, k) \in N^3 : (\mu | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x)) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon)\} = 1,$$

or

$$\delta_2 \{(m, n, k) \in N^3 : (\gamma | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x)) \geq (\beta + \epsilon)\} = 0.$$

Where $B_{mnk}(f, x)$ is Bernstein polynomials of rough statistically A - summable to $f(x)$, then for every $\epsilon > 0$,

$$P - \lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{u,v,w} |\{(m, n, k) \in N^3 : (\mu(P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon)\}| = 1.$$

or

$$P - \lim_{u,v,w \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{u,v,w} |\{(m, n, k) \in N^3 : (\gamma(P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - f(x))) \geq (\beta + \epsilon)\}| = 0.$$

Thus, the triple sequence of Bernstein polynomials of $B_{mnk}(f, x)$ is neutrosophic metric spaces of the triple sequences of rough statistically A - summable to $f(x)$ if and only if $B_{mnk}(f, Ax)$ is neutrosophic metric spaces of the triple sequences of rough statistically convergent to $f(x)$.

4. MAIN RESULTS

4.1. Theorem. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough statistical convergence λ - in the probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ in the universe of discourse F , a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of real numbers of continuous function defined in the closed interval $[0,1]$, then the following are equivalent.

$$(1) B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \rightarrow_{\beta, \lambda}^{[\gamma, \lambda]} f(x, t) \text{ or } B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \rightarrow_{\beta, \lambda}^{[\mu, \lambda]} f(x, t).$$

$$(2) B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \xrightarrow{\beta^{\lambda}}^{S^P} f(x, t) \text{ or } B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \rightarrow_{\beta^{\lambda}}^{S^P} f(x, t).$$

Proof: It is easy to prove and, therefore, is omitted.

4.2. Theorem. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough statistical convergence $\lambda-$ in the probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ in the universe of discourse F , a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of real numbers of continuous function defined in the closed interval $[0,1]$, then the neutrosophic metric spaces of triple sequences of rough $\lambda-$ statistically convergent in probability to a random variable $(B_{mnk}(f, x)) : W \rightarrow R^3$ with respect to the roughness of degree β (or shortly $\beta - \lambda-$ summable in probability to $f(x)$) if for each $\delta > 0$. if

$$(1) B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \xrightarrow{\beta^{\lambda}}^{S^P} f(x, t) \text{ or } B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \rightarrow_{\beta^{\lambda}}^{S^P} f(x, t) \text{ and}$$

$$(2) B_{mnk}(f, y, t) \xrightarrow{\beta^{\lambda}}^{S^P} f(y, t) \text{ or } B_{mnk}(f, y, t) \rightarrow_{\beta^{\lambda}}^{S^P} f(y, t), \text{ then}$$

$$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty}$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_{uvw}} | \{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\mu(P | B_{mnk}(f, x) - B_{mnk}(f, y) |)) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \} | = 1$$

or

$$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty}$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_{uvw}} | \{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\gamma(P | B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - B_{mnk}(f, y, t) |)) \geq (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \} | = 0.$$

equivalently

$$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty}$$

$$\frac{1}{uvw} | \{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\mu(1 - P | B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - B_{mnk}(f, y, t) |)) \geq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \} | = 1.$$

or

$$\lim_{uvw \rightarrow \infty}$$

$$\frac{1}{uvw} | \{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\gamma(1 - P | B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - B_{mnk}(f, y, t) |)) \leq (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \} | = 0.$$

Proof: It is easy to prove and, therefore, is omitted.

4.3. Theorem. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough statistical convergence $\lambda-$ in the probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ in the universe of discourse F , a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of real numbers of continuous function defined in the closed interval $[0,1]$, then the neutrosophic metric spaces of triple sequences of rough $\lambda-$ statistically convergent in probability to a random variable $(B_{mnk}(f, x, t)) : W \rightarrow R^3$ with respect to the roughness of degree β (or shortly $\beta - \lambda-$ summable in probability to $f(x, t)$) if for each $\delta > 0$. if $\lambda \in D-$ is such that $\lim_{uvw} \frac{\lambda_{uvw}}{uvw}$, then

$$B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \xrightarrow{\beta^{\lambda}}^{S^P} f(x, t) \text{ or } B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \rightarrow_{\beta^{\lambda}}^{S^P} f(x, t) \subset B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \xrightarrow{\beta}^{S^P} f(x, t) \text{ or } B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \rightarrow_{\beta}^{S^P} f(x, t).$$

Proof: Let $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$ be given. Since $\lim_{uvw} \frac{\lambda_{uvw}}{uvw} = 1$ we can choose $(r, s, t) \in N^3$ such that $|\frac{\lambda_{uvw}}{uvw} - 1| < \frac{\eta}{2}$ for all $u \geq r, v \geq s, w \geq t$. Now observe that for $\epsilon, \delta > 0$.

$$\frac{1}{uvw} | \{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\mu(P | B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t) |)) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \} | = 1 = \frac{1}{1}$$

| {m ≤ u, n
≤ v, k ≤ w
- λ_{uvw} : (μ
(P | B_{mnk} (f,
x, t) - (f, y, t)
|)) ≤

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 1 \\
 & + \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = \\
 & 1, \\
 & \leq \frac{uvw - \lambda_{uvw}}{uvw} + \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \leq \\
 & 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 1, \\
 & \leq 1 - 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \leq \\
 & 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 1, \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\lambda_{uvw}}{uvw} \times \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \leq \\
 & 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 1, \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{\lambda_{uvw}} \times \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \leq \\
 & 1 - (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 1, \text{ hold for all } u \geq r, v \geq s, v \geq t.
 \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \geq (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = \\
 & 0 \\
 & = \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{m \leq u, n \leq v, k \leq w - \lambda_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \geq \\
 & (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 0 \\
 & + \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \geq (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 0, \\
 & \leq \frac{uvw - \lambda_{uvw}}{uvw} + \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \geq \\
 & (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 0, \\
 & \leq 1 - 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \geq \\
 & (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 0, \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\lambda_{uvw}}{uvw} \times \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \geq \\
 & (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 0, \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{\lambda_{uvw}} \times \frac{1}{uvw} \mid \{(m, n, k) \in Q_{uvw} : (\mu(P \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, y, t))) \geq \\
 & (\beta + \epsilon) \geq \delta \mid = 0, \text{ hold for all } u \geq r, v \geq s, v \geq t. \text{ This completes the proof.}
 \end{aligned}$$

4.4. Theorem. Let $(F, \mu, \gamma, \circ, \cdot)$ be a Bernstein Stancu operator of rough statistical convergence λ - in the probability of neutrosophic metric spaces of vague set (NMV) and β be a non-negative real number, $0 < \epsilon < 1$ and $t > 0$ in the universe of discourse F , a triple sequence of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $(B_{mnk}(f, x))$ of real numbers of continuous function defined in the closed interval $[0, 1]$, then the neutrosophic metric spaces of triple sequences of rough λ - statistically convergent in probability to a random variable $(B_{mnk}(f, x, t)) : W \rightarrow R^3$ with respect to the roughness of degree and $I \subset 2^N$ be an admissible ideal. Then $(I^g - \lim_{\lambda} B_{mnk}(f, x, t)) \neq \phi$ for all $\beta > 0$, an I^g -analytic triple sequence of neutrosophic metric spaces of Bernstein stancu polynomials always contains a sub

sequence $B_{p, q, j}(f, x, t)$ with $I^g - \lim_{\lambda} B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \neq \phi$

Proof: Since the triple sequence of neutrosophic metric spaces of Bernstein polynomials of $B_{mnk}(f, x, t)$ is $I^g - \lambda$ analytic then there exists a positive real number M such that

$$\{(p, q, j) \in (N)^3 : \frac{1}{g(\lambda_{pqj})} \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t)^{1/m+n+k} \mid \geq M\} \in I.$$

Define $\beta = \sup\{(p, q, j) \in (N)^3 : \frac{1}{g(\lambda_{pqj})} \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t)^{1/m+n+k} \mid \geq M : (m, n, k) \in K^c, \}$

where $K = \{(p, q, j) \in (N)^3 : \frac{1}{g(\lambda_{pqj})} \mid B_{mnk}(f, x, t)^{1/m+n+k} \mid \geq M.\}$

Then the set $I^g - \lim_{\lambda} B_{mnk}(f, x, t)$ contains the origin of R^3 . So we have $I^g - \lim_{\lambda} B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \neq \phi$. If $I^g - \lim_{\lambda} B_{mnk}(f, x, t) \neq \phi$ for some $\beta \geq 0$, then

there exists $f(x, t)$ such that $f(x, t) \in I_{\lambda}^g - \text{LIM}^{\beta} B_{mnk}(f, x, t)$,

$$\{(pqj) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : \frac{1}{g(\lambda_{pqj})} (\mu(P | B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, x, t))) \leq 1 - (\beta + \epsilon)\} = 1 \in I$$

or

$$\{(pqj) \in \mathbb{N}^3 : \frac{1}{g(\lambda_{pqj})} (\gamma(P | B_{mnk}(f, x, t) - (f, x, t))) \geq (\beta + \epsilon)\} = 0 \in I \text{ for each}$$

$\epsilon > 0$. Then we say that almost all $B_{mnk}(f, x, t)$ are contained in small ball with any radius greater than β . So the triple sequence spaces of neutrosophic metric spaces of Bernstein stancu polynomials of $B_{mnk}(f, x, t)$ is I_{λ}^g triple analytic sequence space of neutrosophic metric spaces. .

Since $B_{mnk}(f, x, t)$ is a I_{λ}^g triple analytic sequence space of Bernstein stancu polynomials of neutrosophic three dimensional metric spaces, it certainly contains a I_{λ} -convergent of weight g sub sequence $B_{m_i, n_j, k_{\ell}}(f, x, t)$. Let (f, x, t) be its I_{λ} -limit point, then $I_{\lambda}^g - \text{LIM}^{\beta} B_{m_i, n_j, k_{\ell}}(f, x, t) = \bar{B}_{\beta}(f, x, t)$ and, for $\beta > 0$, $I_{\lambda}^g - \text{LIM}^{\beta} B_{m_i, n_j, k_{\ell}}(f, x, t) = \phi$

5. CONCLUSION

A new approach to extend the application area of rough statistical convergence usually used in the triple sequence of Bernstein stancu operator of real numbers to the theory of probability distributions of Bernstein stancu polynomials of rough λ -statistical convergence and Bernstein stancu polynomials of rough strong (V, λ) -summable generalize the convergence analysis. We show that rough statistical convergence in probability is the more generalized concept than usual Bernstein stancu polynomials of rough statistical convergence in neutrosophic metric spaces are examined. Second, we define the statistical summability A of the Bernstein stancu polynomials of the summability RH matrix and prove that it is stronger than Bernstein stancu polynomials of rough statistical convergence of neutrosophic metric spaces for admissible ideal then $I_{\lambda}^g - \text{LIM}^{\beta} B_{mnk}(f, x, t) = \phi$.

6. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in the approval of the research.

This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals conducted by any of the authors.

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